

Lemoine Circles

Professor Ion Patrascu, Fratii Buzesti National College, Craiova, Romania
Professor Florentin Smarandache, New Mexico University, Gallup, NM, USA

In this article, we get to **Lemoine's circles** in a different manner than the known one.

Theorem 1.

Let ABC a triangle and K its simedian center. We take through K the parallel A_1A_2 to BC , $A_1 \in (AB)$, $A_2 \in (AC)$; through A_2 we take the antiparallels A_2B_1 to AB in relation to CA and CB , $B_1 \in (BC)$; through B_1 we take the parallel B_1B_2 to AC , $B_2 \in AB$; through B_2 we take the antiparallels B_1C_1 to BC , $C_1 \in (AC)$, and through C_1 we take the parallel C_1C_2 to AB , $C_2 \in (BC)$. Then:

- i. C_2A_1 is an antiparallel of AC ;
- ii. $B_1B_2 \cap C_1C_2 = \{K\}$;
- iii. The points $A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2$ are concyclical (*the first Lemoine circle*).

Proof.

- i. The quadrilateral BC_2KA is a parallelogram, and its center, i.e. the middle of the segment (C_2A_1) , belongs to the simedian BK ; it follows that C_2A_2 is an antiparallel to AC (see *Figure 1*).
- ii. Let $\{K'\} = A_1A_2 \cap B_1B_2$, because the quadrilateral $K'B_1CA_2$ is a parallelogram; it follows that CK' is a simedian; on the other hand, CK is a simedian, and since $K, K' \in A_1A_2$, it follows that we have $K' = K$.

iii. B_2C_1 being an antiparallel to BC and $A_1A_2 \parallel BC$, it means that B_2C_1 is an antiparallel to A_1A_2 , so the points B_2, C_1, A_2, A_1 are concyclical.

From $B_1B_2 \parallel AC$, $\sphericalangle B_2C_1A \equiv \sphericalangle ABC$, $\sphericalangle B_1A_2C \equiv \sphericalangle ABC$ we get that the quadrilateral $B_2C_1A_2B_1$ is an isosceles trapezoid, so the points B_2, C_1, A_2, B_1 are concyclical.

Analogously, it can be shown that the quadrilateral $C_2B_1A_2A_1$ is an isosceles trapezoid, therefore the points C_2, B_1, A_2, A_1 are concyclical.

Figure 1

From the previous three quartets of concyclical points, it results the concyclicity of the points belonging to *the first Lemoine circle*.

Theorem 2.

In the scalene triangle ABC , let K be the simedian center. We take from K the antiparallel A_1A_2 to BC ; $A_1 \in AB, A_2 \in AC$; through A_2 we build $A_2B_1 \parallel AB$; $B_1 \in (BC)$, then through B_1 we build B_1B_2 the antiparallel to AC , $B_2 \in (AB)$, and through B_2 we build $B_2C_1 \parallel BC$, $C_1 \in AC$, and, finally, through C_1 we take the antiparallel C_1C_2 to AB , $C_2 \in (BC)$. Then:

- i. $C_2A_1 \parallel AC$;
- ii. $B_1B_2 \cap C_1C_2 = \{K\}$;
- iii. The points $A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2$ are concyclical (*the second Lemoine circle*).

Proof.

i. Let $\{K'\} = A_1A_2 \cap B_1B_2$, having $\sphericalangle AA_1A_2 = \sphericalangle ACB$ and $\sphericalangle BB_1B_2 \equiv \sphericalangle BAC$ because A_1A_2 și B_1B_2 are antiparallels to BC, AC , respectively, it follows that $\sphericalangle K'A_1B_2 \equiv \sphericalangle K'B_2A_1$, so $K'A_1 = K'B_2$; having $A_1B_2 \parallel B_1A_2$ as well, it follows that also $K'A_2 = K'B_1$, so $A_1A_2 = B_1B_2$. Because C_1C_2 and B_1B_2 are antiparallels to AB and AC , we have $K''C_2 = K''B_1$; we noted $\{K''\} = B_1B_2 \cap C_1C_2$; since $C_1B_2 \parallel B_1C_2$, we have that the triangle $K''C_1B_2$ is also isosceles, therefore $K''C_1 = C_1B_2$, and we get that $B_1B_2 = C_1C_2$. Let $\{K'''\} = A_1A_2 \cap C_1C_2$; since A_1A_2 and C_1C_2 are antiparallels to BC and AB , we get that the triangle $K'''A_2C_1$ is isosceles, so $K'''A_2 = K'''C_1$, but $A_1A_2 = C_1C_2$ implies that $K'''C_2 = K'''A_1$, then $\sphericalangle K'''A_1C_2 \equiv \sphericalangle K'''A_2C_1$ and, accordingly, $C_2A_1 \parallel AC$.

Figure 2

ii. We noted $\{K'\} = A_1A_2 \cap B_1B_2$; let $\{X\} = B_2C_1 \cap B_1A_2$; obviously, BB_1XB_2 is a parallelogram; if K_0 is the middle of (B_1B_2) , then BK_0 is a simedian,

since B_1B_2 is an antiparallel to AC , and the middle of the antiparallels of AC are situated on the simedian BK . If $K_0 \neq K$, then $K_0K \parallel A_1B_2$ (because $A_1A_2 = B_1B_2$ and $B_1A_2 \parallel A_1B_2$), on the other hand, B, K_0, K are collinear (they belong to the simedian BK), therefore K_0K intersects AB in B , which is absurd, so $K_0 = K$, and, accordingly, $B_1B_2 \cap A_1A_2 = \{K\}$. Analogously, we prove that $C_1C_2 \cap A_1A_2 = \{K\}$, so $B_1B_2 \cap C_1C_2 = \{K\}$.

iii. K is the middle of the congruent antiparallels A_1A_2, B_1B_2, C_1C_2 , so $KA_1 = KA_2 = KB_1 = KB_2 = KC_1 = KC_2$. The simedian center K is the center of *the second Lemoine circle*.

Remark.

The center of *the first Lemoine circle* is the middle of the segment $[OK]$, where O is the center of the circle circumscribed to the triangle ABC . Indeed, the perpendiculars taken from A, B, C on the antiparallels B_2C_1, A_1C_2, B_1A_2 respectively pass through O , the center of the circumscribed circle (the antiparallels have the directions of the tangents taken to the circumscribed circle in A, B, C). The mediatrix of the segment B_2C_1 pass through the middle of B_2C_1 , which coincides with the middle of AK , so is the middle line in the triangle AKO passing through the middle of (OK) . Analogously, it follows that the mediatrix of A_1C_2 pass through the middle L_1 of $[OK]$.

Bibliography.

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